

ITER Project

Improving Thermal Efficiency of hoRizontal ground heat exchangers

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Guidelines on best practice to be adopted in situ for TEBM use

Deliverable 3.1

WP3 Best practice to use thermally enhanced backfilling material (TEBM) on test site

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Introduction

The present guidelines concern the best practice to be adopted in situ for the installation of a special form of ground source collector, the Helix system, and the use of Thermally Enhanced Backfilling Material (TEBM) as backfilling material in very shallow geothermal application.

These best practice are based on the experience acquired on the ITER test site, located in Eltersdorf (Germany), and benefit from skill, expertise and multy-year experience of the two industrial partners of ITER Project, REHAU AG&Co and Fischer Spezialbaustoffe.

REHAU is a world leader in the production of new technological solution for shallow geothermal energy systems. Its innovative products cover various pipe solutions to extract energy from the ground, such as probes for vertical boreholes (up to 150 m deep), horizontal collectors (for large surface areas), Helix probes (for space saving installations), coaxial probes for radial drilling and pipework for thermal piles. There is a proven and consolidated expertise in installing and monitoring shallow geothermal plants all over the world and specially in Germany.

Fischer Spezialbaustoffe is a specialised manufacturer of thermally enhanced grouting/ backfilling material for geothermal probes. The research activities are devoted to products characterized by a high thermal value and a proven frost-thaw stability, ensuring an excellent connection of the probe to the underground and enabling a sustainable efficiency of the geothermal system

In the ITER Project test site 2 main innovations are pursued:

1. laying a Helix horizontally rather than vertically, in order to check its behavior as a horizontal collector for very shallow geothermal installations;
2. the use of 2 natural TEBMs mixtures, obtained mixing sand and clay materials in different percentages, tested also during the laboratory phase of the project, and one commercial thermally enhanced product in the same environmental conditions.

The better way to dispose of these elements, as defined by ITER Project, is hereafter described.

1. Horizontal collectors and special forms

Very shallow geothermal (VSG) systems, as horizontal collectors or special forms, are conceived coupled with a ground source heat pump (GSHP) to exploit renewable energy in the form of heat from the first 2 m of depth from the ground level, for heating or cooling the buildings.

The ground-source energy relies on the near constant temperature of the ground throughout the year and is continuously regeneration from solar radiation, rainfall and, for a lesser extent, from the geothermal heat flow from the interior of the earth ($\approx 0.015 - 0.1 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$). Then, in order to favor the heat regeneration of the ground, the ground source collectors are preferentially used in a combined mode for heating/cooling and the surface on top of them is generally left unsealed.

In the design and planning of a VSG system it is possible to discern several phases, synthesized as follow:

1. Planning / Design / Sizing
2. Laying / Installation / Construction / Assembly
3. Backfilling
4. Testing / Operating mode

1. Planning / Design / Sizing

This phase consists of identifying the heat source available at the site, selecting the heating system and auxiliary equipment according to the building thermal needs, the geological conditions, the official requirements (laws and regulations, protection areas...) and the construction space availability.

A good knowledge of geology and hydrogeology allows to determine the thermal and hydraulic properties of the substrate and therefore to select the suitable extraction techniques according to the heating and cooling needs of the building (i.e. heating/cooling loads of the building, heat pump type (COP), flow rate, specific extracted power, operating hours ...).

2. Laying / Installation / Construction / Assembly

According to VDI 4640, the pipes of ground-source collector systems should be laid at a depth of 1.2 – 1.5m and with spacing of 0.3 - 0.8m. The necessary earthworks can usually be carried out using conventional construction machines.

In addition, the special forms or horizontal collectors are subjected to a visual inspection prior to starting installation, because if damaged, they must not be installed. Then, if they are made of high-quality material, they are placed directly at the bottom of the trench and a sand bed is not required.

Moreover, the ground source solutions must not be built over or laid under sealed areas in order to allow soil heat regeneration (favored by climatic influences near to the surface) and they should be placed at a sufficient distance from trees, bushes and sensitive plants.

3. Backfilling

Once VSG systems are placed, the trench must be filled in.

As backfilling material, it is possible to use directly the excavated soil, if suitably cohesive and if the heat collectors present a high resistance to stress (puncture loads). As alternative, sand with a grain size ranging between 0-3 mm is usually used. In addition, if saturated soil is available, the performance of the system increases.

The backfilling then takes place step by step. A good contact between the VSG systems and the surrounding ground must be achieved, reducing the occurrence of air pockets in order to enhance the thermal conductivity and ensure the required extraction output.

In addition, the ground around the collectors must be compacted sufficiently to avoid negative effect on the energy yield. However, it is suggested to start this procedure only when the bedding layer covering the VSG systems reaches a thickness of at least 0.3 m.

4. Connections / Testing / Operating mode

Finally, the whole system must be subjected to a suitable, final pressure test, e.g. to EN 805, once all connections have been created

After a successful pressure test, the connection to the liquid manifold takes place and the unit is filled with prepared heat transfer fluid (e.g. ethylene glycol).

During the ITER Project, laying the Helix horizontally, the main efforts have been devoted defining the best practices for phase 2 and 3, that is for installation and backfilling procedures, described in the following paragraphs.

2. Helix unit

The Helix unit produced by REAHU is a ground-source system conceived for use in both new buildings and also refurbishments of existing ones. According to the VDI Guidelines 4640 it is considered as a special form of ground-source collector.

In general, it is used inserted vertically in a borehole, when a small land area is available and probe drilling is not possible for geological reasons or if it is not financially viable. In ITER Project test site this special form has been layed horizontally, so the installation procedure differs from the one generally suggested by the producer. In fact, due to its characteristics, used in this way the Helix can be an ideal solution also when insufficient space is available for installing a conventional horizontal collector.

2.1 Helix characteristics

The Helix unit is made of cross-linked polyethylene (PE-Xa), a material particularly resistant to mechanical damage, ensuring the highest possible reliability and efficiency during transport, installation and in operation, and having a high temperature resistance (up to +95 °C). The Helix is delivered in a 1.1m long coil, which is extended to 3m in length on site, reducing significantly the related costs for storage and transportation (Fig.1). The pipe spacing is kept constant through the spiral extrusion, held together with binding.

The average extraction performance to be achieved, largely influenced by the type of soil and groundwater present, is about 400 W/Helix (up to 700W/ Helix in optimum conditions).

Figure 1: REHAU Helix: technical data and view of compact and extended unit with colored flow (blue) and return (red) connections (modified by REHAU).

Due to high resistance to stress (puncture loads), as backfilling is possible to adopt the excavated material and sand bed is not required. Moreover, it is quite simple to install in a horizontal way, requiring less approvals and groundworks.

2.2 Guidelines for horizontal Helix installation

The horizontal installation of the Helix is carried out as follow:

1. Trench excavation

- use of conventional construction machines (i.e. digger) for creating a trench
 - excavation of a trench 5.0 m long, 1.1 m depth (frost free area) and 1.2 m wide for one Helix
 - minimum distance between 2 Helix 0.8 m
 - laying depth ca. 1.1 m from ground level, in line with DIN 18302 and DIN 4124
- casing generally not required

2. Preparation and insertion of Helix

- extend probes to installation length of ca. 3 m
 - check the helix for damage
 - insert the completely extended Helix into the trench
 - securing Helix in the trench
 - the distance of the collectors from other supply lines, buildings etc. must be at least 70cm
 - the helix must be installed at a sufficient distance away from trees, shrubs and plants
- no plants with deep roots should be planted above the Helix field in order to prevent any negative effects on the functionality of the Helix as well as the vegetation

3. Backfilling of the trench

- backfill by hand to avoid creation of voids between the helix and the trench wall
- if the helix is made of a material resistant to crack formations, it is possible to use the excavated material as backfill
- the distribution of the backfilling material must be as much as possible homogenous, to avoid cavities occurrence and to enhance the thermal conductivity: it is suggested to cover the helix with thin horizontal strata (i.e. 10 cm) applied step by step until the ground level is reached
- once the bedding layer covers the helix at least for 0.30 m, the soil could be compacted using light equipment

4. Connections:

- flow rate and pressure test on each individual Helix at end of installation
- connection of the different fluid circuits to manifold
- filling in the Helix unit with a prepared water-glycol solution

2.3 Guidelines for backfilling with TEBM mixtures

The performance of a vSG system is strongly correlated to the kind of sediment at disposal (mineralogical composition, grain size distribution, bulk density, moisture content) and suddenly decreases in case of dry-unsaturated conditions in the surrounding soil. The specific extraction power depends on the different soil and groundwater conditions and on the annual operating period.

In order to improve the heat exchange between soil and horizontal heat collector, in the framework of ITER projects several Thermally Enhanced Backfilling Material (TEBM) have been tested in laboratory.

Some of them have been selected to be tested in situ in the test field, in detail, one mixture composed of fine sand and clay and one commercial product.

Here are described the suggested steps for in situ application of both TEBM types.

2.3.1 Backfilling with natural mixtures

Natural TEBM employed in ITER Project, as already defined in DL2.1, consists of sand material (fine sand 0-1 mm or sand 0-5 mm) mixed with clay material, up to 15% in weight.

To prepare this mixture directly in situ it is recommended:

1. Material collection

- have at disposal the right amount of sand (0-5mm or 0-1 mm) and clay material (bentonite or clay), easily available on the market for building construction purpose;

2. TEBM preparation on site

- use a standardized concrete mixer;

- mix sand and bentonite in accordance with the percentages defined in DL2.1 (in this case 85% sand and 15% bentonite in weight);

3.filling the trench on site

- transport the TEBM to the trench;
- distribute TEBM as much as possible in a homogenous way, to avoid creation of air pockets;
- proceed by creating thin horizontal strata (i.e. 10 cm) applied step by step up to the ground level; moreover, as seen in laboratory (DL2.1) it is recommended to wet each layer in a homogeneous manner to saturate slightly the soil and avoid initial completely dry conditions, unfavorable to heat transfer;

4.compaction and connections

- compact the soil
- connect the probes to manifold and the measuring systems to datalogger
- perform flow rate and pressure test

2.3.2 Backfilling with commercial product

1. Material preparation

- have at disposal (i) the right amount of commercial backfilling material to cover the Helix and (ii) all the devices necessary to prepare the product;

2. Commercial product preparation on site (according to producer guidelines)

- surround the Helix with a removable containment system (i.e. wooden panels) in order to define the volume to be filled in with the commercial product;
- following the producer guidelines, prepare the commercial product mixing it with water using a devoted mixing machine. In Eltersdorf the Fischer GeoSolid 240 HS thermally optimized material (for sulfate-aggressive groundwater, with a declared thermal conductivity of $2.4 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$, in compliance with VDI 4640, and DIN 12390/9) has been used;

3.covering the helix

- pump the mixture using a pump-tube directly connected to the mixture device in order to cover completely the Helix, avoiding the creation of air pockets;

4.filling the trench on site

- once the Helix is completely covered and the thermal optimized material dried up, it is possible to remove the containment system and fill in the trench up to the ground level with excavated material

4.compaction and connections

- compact the soil
- connect the probes to manifold and the measuring systems to datalogger
- perform flow rate and pressure test

3. References

1. REHAU Unlimited Polymer Solutions (2017). *RAUGEO Ground-Source Systems - Technical Information*. REHAU AG&Co Eds.
2. REHAU Unlimited Polymer Solutions (2017). *RAUGEO Helix Probe PE-Xa – Innovative Ground-Source Energy Extraction*. REHAU AG&Co Eds.
3. REHAU Unlimited Polymer Solutions (2017). *RAUGEO Ground-Source Solutions - Renewable source of heating and cooling*. REHAU AG&Co Eds.
4. REHAU Unlimited Polymer Solutions (2015). *RAUGEO Ground Loop Heat Exchange System - Technical Manual*. REHAU AG&Co Eds.
5. REHAU Unlimited Polymer Solutions (2014). *RAUGEO Ground-Source Systems Innovative Heating & Cooling Solutions - PARTS LIST 827300/12 EN*. REHAU AG&Co Eds.
6. Banks, D. (2012). *An introduction to thermogeology: ground source heating and cooling*. John Wiley & Sons